

International Conference on Data Mining and NLP (DNLP 2020)

November 28 ~ 29, 2020, Dubai, UAE

<https://aisca2020.org/dnlp/index.html>

Scope & Topics

International Conference on Data Mining and NLP (DNLP 2020) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and applications of Data mining and NLP. The goal of this conference is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on understanding Data mining and NLP concepts and establishing new collaborations in these areas.

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the areas of data mining and NLP.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following:

- Data Mining Applications
- Data Mining in Modeling, Visualization, Personalization, and Recommendation
- Data Mining Systems and Platforms, Efficiency, Scalability, and Privacy
- Foundations, Algorithms, Models, and Theory
- Mining Text, Semi-Structured, Spatio -Temporal, Streaming, Graph, Web, Multimedia
- Knowledge Processing
- Chunking/Shallow Parsing
- Dialog Systems
- Discourse
- Information Extraction
- Information Retrieval
- Lexical Semantics
- Linguistic Resources
- Machine Translation
- Ontology
- Paraphrasing/Entailment/Generation
- Parsing/Grammatical Formalisms
- Phonology, Morphology
- POS Tagging
- Question Answering
- Semantic Processing
- Speech Recognition and Synthesis
- Spoken Language Processing
- Statistical and Knowledge based Methods
- Text Mining
- NLP and Machine Learning
- NLP and Computational Linguistics
- NLP and Information Retrieval
- NLP and AI, Data Mining

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **September 06, 2020**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [Computer Science Conference Proceedings](#) in [Computer Science & Information Technology \(CS & IT\)](#) series (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **DNLP 2020**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issues of the following journals

- [International Journal on Natural Language Computing\(IJNLC\)](#)
- [International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology \(IJWesT\)](#)
- [International Journal of Database Management Systems \(IJDMS\)](#)
- [International Journal of Data Mining & Knowledge Management Process \(IJDMP\)](#)
- [Advanced Computing: An International Journal \(ACIJ\)](#)
- [Information Technology in Industry \(ITII\)^{New}](#) - ESCI(WOS) Indexed

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : September 06, 2020**
- Authors Notification : October 15, 2020
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : October 23, 2020

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us : dnlpconf@yahoo.com or dnlp@aisca2020.org